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Digital Revolution: Generation Z under Project REALM

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Known as "digital natives," today's elementary students in Generation Z possess advanced digital abilities that could potentially transform conventional teaching methods. In fact, the Grade 6 students from Gun-ob Elementary School of Lapu-Lapu City Division, who were chosen for Project REALM (Responsive Adaptive Experiential Learning Method), a school innovation program, transformed the way technology was used to produce amazing results during both in-person and online activities.

The class known as Batch Hydra, which is adapting to the hybrid mode of learning, is made up of pre-selected students who completed several qualifying tasks prior to the start of the academic year. Activities included using apps and online support systems that would eventually be a regular part of their educational schedule. To assist the program's pilot testing, qualifying pupils also had their parents pre-informed about the documented program.

With the use of Pure Activity Learning Method (PALM) as an expressive method of instruction, students participated in inclusive experience activities like creating digital art throughout the first semester. Students create works of art that range from abstract and portrait to surrealistic, using their gadgets like cellphones and tablets during man-to-man sessions or asynchronous offline activities at home. Additionally, students created digital advocacy materials like project plans, posters, and slogans. Additionally, an online weekend learner's poll was employed to collect output and provide feedback.

What made them different from other schools is that this project was crafted to aid the learning discrepancies of students as well as provide means of actual interest to the present generation -- an interest that would spark their learning. With this purpose, learners became more competent especially when challenged to solve academic hindrances. Also, the batch became achievers winning from various school to school competitions be it in academic, sports, journalism, talent showcase, and other areas.

One of Batch Hydra's students, Kael Ondrei T. Cabalhug, showed interest in REALM even though it differs from typical teaching and learning methods. "I'm very

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happy and privileged to be working on this project. It inspires me to pursue further learning. Our teacher helps us to

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